

OPEN LETTER

REVISED Data formats and standards for opportunistic rainfall sensors [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]

Martin Fencel¹, Roberto Nebuloni², Jafet C. M. Andersson³, Vojtech Bares¹, Nico Blettner^{4,5}, Greta Cazzaniga⁶, Christian Chwala⁴, Matteo Colli⁷, Lotte de Vos⁸, Abbas El Hachem⁹, Charles Galdies¹⁰, Filippo Giannetti¹¹, Maximilian Graf^{4,5}, Dror Jacoby¹², Hai Victor Habi¹², Petr Musil¹³, Jonatan Ostrometzky¹², Giacomo Roversi^{14,15}, Fabiola Sapienza¹¹, Jochen Seidel⁹, Anna Spackova¹, Remco van de Beek³, Bas Walraven¹⁶, Karina Wilgan¹⁷, Xin Zheng^{12,18}

¹Department of Hydraulics and Hydrology, Czech Technical University in Prague, Prague 6, 16629, Czech Republic

²IEIIT-CNR (National Research Council of Italy), Milano, Italy

³Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Gothenburg, Sweden

⁴Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research, Campus Alpin, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany

⁵Chair of Regional Climate and Hydrology, Institute of Geography, University Augsburg, Augsburg, Germany

⁶Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Lombardy, Italy

⁷Artys srl, Genova, Italy

⁸Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute, de Bilt, Netherlands Antilles

⁹Institute for Modelling Hydraulic and Environmental Systems, University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany

¹⁰Institute of Earth Systems, University of Malta, Msida, Malta

¹¹Department of Information Engineering, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

¹²School of Electrical Engineering, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv-Yafo, Tel Aviv District, Israel

¹³Brno University of Technology, Brno, Czech Republic

¹⁴ISAC-CNR (National Research Council of Italy), Roma, Italy

¹⁵Department of Physics and Astronomy "Augusto Righi", University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

¹⁶Department of Water Management, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands Antilles

¹⁷GFZ Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

¹⁸State Key Laboratory of Hydrology-Water Resources and Hydraulic Engineering, Center for Global Change and Water Cycle, Hohai University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China

v2 First published: 10 Oct 2023, 3:169
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16068.1>
 Latest published: 13 Feb 2024, 3:169
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16068.2>

Abstract

Opportunistic sensors are increasingly used for rainfall measurement. However, their raw data are collected by a variety of systems that are often not primarily intended for rainfall monitoring, resulting in a plethora of different data formats and a lack of common standards. This hinders the sharing of opportunistic sensing (OS) data, their automated processing, and, at the end, their practical usage and

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 2 (revision) 13 Feb 2024		 view
version 1 10 Oct 2023		

integration into standard observation systems. This paper summarises the experiences of the more than 100 members of the OpenSense Cost Action involved in the OS of rainfall. We review the current practice of collecting and storing precipitation OS data and corresponding metadata, and propose new common guidelines describing the requirements on data and metadata collection, harmonising naming conventions, and defining human-readable and machine readable file formats for data and metadata storage. We focus on three sensors identified by the OpenSense community as prominent representatives of the OS of precipitation: Commercial microwave links (CML): fixed point-to-point radio links mainly used as backhauling connections in telecommunication networks Satellite microwave links (SML): radio links between geostationary Earth orbit (GEO) satellites and ground user terminals. Personal weather stations (PWS): non-professional meteorological sensors owned by citizens. The conventions presented in this paper are primarily designed for storing, handling, and sharing historical time series and do not consider specific requirements for using OS data in real time for operational purposes. The conventions are already now accepted by the ever growing OpenSense community and represent an important step towards automated processing of OS raw data and community development of joint OS software packages.

Plain language summary

Opportunistic sensors, devices primarily intended not intended for sensing, are increasingly used for rainfall measurement. The lack of conventions defining which data should be stored and how, makes it difficult to automatically process the data and integrate these observations into standard monitoring networks. This paper reviews current practice of collecting and storing precipitation opportunistic sensing (OS) data based on the experience of more than 100 members of the OpenSense Cost Action and suggest common data format standards. We focus on three sensors identified by the OpenSense community as prominent representatives of the OS of precipitation: Commercial microwave links (CML), Satellite Microwave Links (SML), and Personal Weather Stations (PWS). The conventions are already now accepted by the ever growing OpenSense community and represent an important step towards automated processing of OS raw data and community development of joint OS software packages.

Keywords

opportunistic rainfall sensing, data standards, data format, naming conventions, commercial microwave links, satellite microwave links, personal weather stations

This article is included in the [COST Actions gateway](#).

1	2
view	view
1. Cristian Lussana ,	
The Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Oslo, Norway	
2. Swastika Chakraborty , Narula Institute of Technology, Kolkata, India	
Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.	

Corresponding author: Martin Fencl (martin.fencl@cvut.cz)

Author roles: **Fencl M:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Nebuloni R:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Methodology, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **C. M. Andersson J:** Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Bares V:** Data Curation, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Blettner N:** Data Curation, Software, Writing – Review & Editing; **Cazzaniga G:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Chwala C:** Conceptualization, Software, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Colli M:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **de Vos L:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **El Hachem A:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Galdies C:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Giannetti F:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Graf M:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Software, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Jacoby D:** Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Victor Habi H:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Musil P:** Conceptualization, Methodology; **Ostrometzky J:** Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Roversi G:** Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Sapienza F:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Seidel J:** Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Spackova A:** Data Curation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **van de Beek R:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Walraven B:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – Review & Editing; **Wilgan K:** Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Zheng X:** Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No CA20136 (Opportunistic precipitation sensing network [OpenSense]).

Copyright: © 2024 Fencl M *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Fencl M, Nebuloni R, C. M. Andersson J *et al.* **Data formats and standards for opportunistic rainfall sensors [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]** Open Research Europe 2024, 3:169 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16068.2>

First published: 10 Oct 2023, 3:169 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16068.1>

REVISED Amendments from Version 1

The revised version takes into account the reviewers' comments. In particular, a chapter discussing OS data availability has been added. The potential of the OS sensors in terms of the number of observations is then further developed. The conclusions of the paper then more strongly reflect the potential benefits of the proposed data format for OS data owners. With respect to the data format conventions themselves, a new discussion is given on how to avoid possible duplicate IDs when merging independent datasets.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this article are those of the authors. Publication in Open Research Europe does not imply endorsement of the European Commission.

Introduction

Characterising the spatial and temporal variability of rainfall represents a challenge in many areas where precipitation plays a key role, such as meteo-hydrology, climatology, weather forecasting, and water management (Ahrens, 2012; Ochoa-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2015). Opportunistic sensing (OS) can complement standard precipitation measuring systems by crowd-sourced observations from personal weather stations or by sensors not primarily intended for precipitation monitoring, such as microwave wireless links. The number of opportunistic sensors has already exceeded the number of conventional instruments by an order of magnitude and is still increasing (ECC, 2016; Lorenz & Kunstmann, 2012; Muller *et al.*, 2015; Tauro *et al.*, 2018). This paper focuses on three types of opportunistic sensors:

- Commercial microwave links (CML),
- satellite microwave links (SML),
- personal weather stations (PWS).

CMLs are point-to-point terrestrial radio links used as the backhaul of mobile networks. They operate at frequencies where radio waves are significantly attenuated by rain which enables their use as opportunistic rainfall sensors. SMLs are space-to-ground links (also, termed downlinks) between geostationary Earth orbit (GEO) telecommunication satellites (SatComs) providing one-way direct-to-home (DTH) TV broadcast or two-way broadband services (*i.e.* satellite internet), and ground-based user terminals. Like CMLs, they operate at frequencies sensitive to raindrops and therefore they can be used for OS. Finally, PWS are non-professional meteorological sensors owned and operated by citizens. They are often equipped with rain gauges that directly measure rainfall. These three types of devices are extensively deployed worldwide and their potential for observing rainfall has been thoroughly investigated (Bárdossy *et al.*, 2021; Chwala & Kustmann, 2019; Colli *et al.*, 2019; de Vos *et al.*, 2017; Giannetti & Reggiannini, 2021).

Opportunistic sensors can potentially provide a massive number of observations. There is about 10 million CMLs, largely operated by mobile network operators or internet providers, deployed around the globe (Ericsson, 2022). The global amount of SMLs providing two-way broadband services is difficult to estimate as the market with satellite internet dynamically evolves and the exact figures are subjected to trade confidentiality. However, the number of satellite internet subscribers has exceeded several millions and will likely exponentially grow (Ernst & Young, 2023), thus, there might be already now a few million of SMLs potentially utilizable as opportunistic sensors. Finally, the global number of PWSs of all brands is expected to be a few hundred thousand (Overeem *et al.*, 2023). CMLs and PWSs have highest density in populated areas, on the other hand, SML ground terminal are often deployed in remote locations. Worldwide, all three types of opportunistic sensors can potentially provide millions of observations every few minute. Currently, only a fraction of this data is used for OS of precipitation.

One of the major challenges of the OS is a lack of data standardisation. For instance, both CML and broadband services SML data are owned by private companies and generated for network monitoring purposes (let us notice that SML data can be freely collected by the users themselves in case of broadcast satellite downlinks). PWS data are collected by non-professional equipment of various manufacturers. These circumstances result in a plethora of different data standards and formats. In light of using OS data for research purposes, but also for future integration with datasets collected by conventional sensors, there is a strong need towards defining common data formats, standards and procedures for opportunistic rainfall sensors. This is one of the core objectives of the European COST Action [OpenSense](#) (CA20136) which was launched in 2021 to build a worldwide reference OS community.

In this paper, we review current OS data collection practices and formats as drawn from the experience of the more than 100 members of the [OpenSense](#) community and provide new guidelines which unify naming conventions, define mandatory, recommended and optional parameters to be stored, and propose netCDF as a common format for handling OS data. Moreover, we suggest a structure of netCDF files for CML, SML and PWS which define how to store data and metadata. Finally, we provide basic recommendations on how to store data in a non-binary (human-readable) form as CSV files. The review of data collection practices as well as the guidelines are based on an online survey performed within [OpenSense](#) Action, the personal experience of the authors, and discussions during dedicated joint [OpenSense](#) meetings of Working group on data management and standardization and Working group on method and software homogenization, which were held within the first and the second year of the Action, *i.e.*, in 2021 and 2022.

The paper is organised as follows. The section below describes the basic principles of operation of the three OS sensors

considered here. Section Current practices in OS data collection overviews current practices in OS data collection. In section Proposed data and metadata standards we propose technical specifications for the information provided by opportunistic sensors. This section is followed by section recommending data formats, *i.e.*, how information should be structured, and finally, we conclude in the last section with the expected impact of the proposed guidelines.

Opportunistic rainfall sensors

This section addresses the principles of CML, SML and PWS as rainfall sensors, as well as main features of the acquired data. An important difference between CML/SML and PWS is that microwave links carry out indirect measurements of rainfall, moving from electrical quantities. On the other hand, PWS are often equipped with simple rain gauges that collect raindrops and directly measure their volume. Figure 1a–c sketches how each of the three sensors work in detecting precipitation, whereas Table 1 summarises their main features.

Commercial microwave links

CMLs are fixed point-to-point line-of-sight radio links mainly used as backhauling links in telecommunication networks, *i.e.*, connecting distributed radio access nodes with the

backbone of the network. Even though wireless backhauling links are being replaced with fibre optic in densely populated areas, the number of nodes is increasing due to network densification to support the innovative 5G technologies. Moreover, they remain dominant in many other contexts, covering large areas of land. CMLs are sometimes used to provide ‘last-mile’ internet connectivity or to provide building-to-building connectivity in LANs. Every CML provides bidirectional transmission between two radio units, that is, the two antennas in Figure 1a work as both transmitting and receiving terminals. Sometimes, dual frequency or multi-frequency links are used meaning that links transmit in each direction over several different frequency (or polarisation) channels (ITU-R, 2017). In Figure 1 the term sublink is used to distinguish among all the possible signals travelling between the same pair of antennas.

CML have lengths of less than 100 metres up to tens of kilometres and most commonly use frequencies between 6 and 95 GHz (ITU-R, 2017). At these frequencies, electromagnetic waves are scattered and absorbed by atmospheric particles. Specifically, rain droplets are responsible for producing a significant decrease of received signal power, often referred to as signal attenuation in engineering. This decrease depends

Figure 1. Sketch of the principle of operation of opportunistic rainfall sensors: **a)** commercial microwave links (CML), **b)** satellite microwave links (SML), and **c)** personal weather stations (PWS).

Table 1. Main features of opportunistic rainfall sensors.

Sensor	Raw data	Spatial Integration	Domain size / location	Temporal Integration	Integration Time
Commercial microwave links	Received power level (RSL) and transmitted power level (TSL)	Straight line	From less than 100 m to few tens of km / tens of m above ground	Instantaneous values, averages or extremes	≤15 min
Satellite microwave links	RSL or SNR	Straight line (slant path)	Several km / near ground to rain height	Instantaneous values or averages	≤1 min
Personal weather stations	Rainfall depth (or rainfall intensity)	Single point Measurement	approx. 1 dm ² / few metres above ground	Sum (or averages)	≥ 5 min

on rainfall intensity according to the following power-law relationship (ITU-R, 2005; Olsen *et al.*, 1978):

$$\gamma = \alpha R^\beta \quad (1)$$

where R is rainfall intensity in mm/h, γ is rain attenuation per unit path length, in units of dB/km, and α and β are coefficients dependent on CML frequency and polarisation, among others. When CMLs are used as opportunistic rainfall sensors, rain attenuation is extracted from CML raw data, and used in Equation (1) to get R . The raw data are received power level (RSL) and transmitted power level (TSL) across each CML. Equation (1), in practical terms, estimates signal attenuation due to rainfall by comparing RSL during rain with RSL (namely the baseline level) measured during clear-sky conditions. Moreover, before applying Equation (1), effects unrelated to rain, such as extra signal attenuation produced by wet antennas, must be filtered out. CML rainfall measurement is a spatial average across the straight path between antennas. Finally, rainfall intensity can be estimated as a (nearly) instantaneous value, an average, or an extreme value over a certain period of time, depending on the raw data collection protocol. Thanks to the large number of CMLs in telecommunication networks, rainfall observations by CMLs can be made over country-wide areas (Graf *et al.*, 2019; Overeem *et al.*, 2013).

It is worth remarking that, CML attenuation can be also utilized to classify precipitation type (Ostrometzky *et al.*, 2015), estimate water vapor content along their path (Fencl & Bares, 2021; Rubin *et al.*, 2022), or detect fog (David *et al.*, 2015).

TSL and RSL measurements are collected by telecom companies, usually in aggregated form and retained only for short periods, as they are essentially used for network monitoring and maintenance. Nonetheless, historical measurement records are starting to be utilized for developing automated solutions optimizing network performance, power consumptions, or site visits (Ericsson, 2023).

What inhibits most companies from sharing TSL and RSL measurements are confidentiality concerns, typically regarding antenna locations, and fears of additional efforts or costs in setting up and running a data collection system, or simply lacking business models for monetizing such data. However, there are several examples in the OpenSense community of how these issues have been overcome. Furthermore, it is foreseen that the concept of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC), which will be an intrinsic element of new-generation 5G/6G systems (Liu *et al.*, 2022), will facilitate offering sensing as a service.

Satellite microwave links

SMLs are part of SatCom systems and are typically used for broadcasting television or for providing two-way broadband connectivity over the broad satellite footprint coverage area. Licensed frequency bands for the downlink of SatCom

services are in the Ku- and Ka-bands, that is, 10-13 GHz and 18–21 GHz, respectively. When working as opportunistic rainfall sensors, SMLs rely on the same principle as CMLs, which is radio wave attenuation due to rain (Giannetti & Reggiannini, 2021). However, there are a few important differences with respect to CMLs:

- One of the two link terminals is a GEO satellite, while the other is a ground-based user terminal (Figure 1b). Hence, only a small fraction of the propagation path is affected by rain (a GEO satellite is located about 36,000 km above ground).
- TSL data from the satellite terminal is usually not available, hence rainfall must only be extracted from RSL or from an equivalent quantity called the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) evaluated at the receiver site.
- RSL (or SNR) exhibit time-varying behaviour not ascribable to atmospheric effects, but due instead to the causes addressed hereafter.

In principle, links based on low/medium Earth orbit satellites could be used as opportunistic rainfall sensors, too. In this case, the space-located transmitting terminals move across the sky. However, here we consider only GEO satellite links for three reasons: 1) they are a simple case of fixed point-to-point link resembling CMLs, 2) SML reception is possible with low-cost commercial-grade equipment for direct satellite broadcasting reception, and 3) the available literature on the topic is limited to GEO satellites.

With slant propagation paths, the layered structure of the troposphere should be taken into account (*e.g.*, including melting layer effects). A key parameter to derive rainfall estimates from an SML is rain height, that is the height above ground where all the solid precipitation melts into liquid rain, which is closely related to the 0°C isotherm height. Unwanted received signal oscillations are due to a number of factors: 1) periodic satellite housekeeping manoeuvres; 2) TSL adjustments occasionally made by the operator; and 3) apparent fluctuations of the satellite position in the sky caused by gravitational perturbations affecting the geostationary orbit. All these signal fluctuations must be filtered out by ad-hoc pre-processing of the raw data.

A signal representing clear-sky conditions, *i.e.*, an undisturbed signal level received in an ideal case of no attenuation caused by the hydrometeors during the precipitation event, is used as the reference level for rain attenuation calculation. This reference level can be evaluated analytically, *e.g.*, based upon nominal values derived from link-budget, or approximated by RSL (or SNR) before the event, or, again, computed from signal statistics of the dry days before the event (Colli *et al.*, 2020).

An advantage of SML-based rainfall measurements is that they usually have a high temporal resolution in the order of 1 or more readings per minute. SML data can be collected by the user terminals and transferred through the terrestrial network,

or they can be sent back from many user terminals through the satellite to the gateway stations and there collected. Finally, it is important to note that for each GEO broadcast satellite there is a multitude of active transponders and that tens of satellites are in visibility on the GEO arc in the sky (see [Giannetti & Reggiannini, 2021](#), Figure 2), hence greatly expanding SML data-gathering options.

Personal weather stations

A PWS is a privately owned weather station which can be set up by users typically comprising one, or a set of, low-cost device(s) recording meteorological variables, as shown in [Figure 1](#). Many popular types of PWS measure rain with an unheated plastic tipping bucket rain gauge. They often have a smaller orifice opening than standard tipping bucket rain gauges ([Bárdossy et al., 2021](#)). Since these devices are not heated, their usefulness is limited to wet precipitation. The tips of the tipping bucket that correspond to a given amount of precipitation are recorded for regular or, in some cases, irregular time intervals. This information yields the total amount of precipitation for a given time interval.

The precision and accuracy of a specific measuring instrument usually follows the manufacturer's specifications. For example, for Netatmo PWS, which is one of the most common types, rain gauges can deliver observations as multiples of the volume of one tip, which, by default, is 0.101 mm, but may differ when a PWS owner has calibrated the device to a different amount. Accuracy would need to be regularly checked to ensure its preciseness ([de Vos et al., 2019a](#)). In previous studies ([de Vos et al., 2017](#); [de Vos et al., 2019a](#)), when PWS rainfall measurements were compared to co-located operational reference rain gauges, rounded measurements were found to be as accurate as operational rain gauges, provided the PWS instruments were properly installed.

PWS are an important OS source as it is possible for PWS owners to share (and visualise) observations in real-time to online platforms. Some examples are the [Wundermap](#) by Weather Underground, the [Netatmo platform](#), the [WOW platform](#), and smaller start-up companies, such as [FieldSense](#) or [Weathercloud](#). The platforms thereby give access to large amounts of in-situ weather observations. In the case of Netatmo, the platform is provided by the company and sharing data requires very little effort which has resulted in an extremely dense international PWS network. It should be noted that while PWS observations are provided and shared by PWS owners, the data are owned by the commercial companies that maintain the platform where data are collected. For researchers and the national weather service, this means a dependency on third parties and uncertainties in the exact processing of the data.

Other opportunistic sensors

Even though this paper focuses on three types of opportunistic sensors, it is worth noting that there are other promising technologies which could be used for the OS of precipitation. For example, recent advances in image processing have enabled quantifying rainfall intensity from recordings

of surveillance cameras ([Dong et al., 2017](#)). Opportunistic sensors can also measure more environmental variables than rainfall which are, however, correlated with rain.

A prominent example is the use of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) for estimating water vapour profiles ([Guerova et al., 2016](#)). The delay of the signal propagating through the atmosphere is related to its refractive index, which, in turn, depends on water vapour content. A ground-based network of GPS receivers can provide near real-time observations suitable for assimilation into Numerical Weather Models (NWMs) and climate applications. Several studies incorporated GNSS into the monitoring of severe weather events, especially those related to precipitation (*e.g.*, [Douša et al., 2016](#)). [Brenot et al. \(2013\)](#) have presented the usefulness of GPS tropospheric gradients as preliminary signs of deep convection and, recently, GNSS time series have been used as indicators of precipitation in a climate region with a high annual precipitation amount ([Li et al., 2021](#); [Zhao et al., 2018](#)). Interest in GNSS meteorology was demonstrated in COST Action 716 "Exploitation of ground-based GPS for operational weather prediction and climate applications" (1999–2004, [Elgered, 2001](#)) and COST Action ES1206 "Advanced GNSS Tropospheric Products for Monitoring Severe Weather Events and Climate" (2013–2017, [Jones et al., 2020](#)). For other OS techniques see *e.g.*, [Muller et al. \(2015\)](#), [Tauro et al. \(2018\)](#), or [Zheng et al. \(2018\)](#).

Current practices in OS data collection

The focus of this section is on the data collection methods of opportunistic rainfall measurements and how data are stored and made available. CML and SML are part of a telecommunication network where TSL, RSL and SNR of individual links are routinely collected by network operators through specific protocols for the purposes of network monitoring and resource optimization. The above raw data are typically stored as time series. To derive rainfall information, CML and SML require additional metadata from the network (*e.g.*, sensor position) and additional data from external sources. In contrast, PWSs provide direct rainfall measurements. Data from many PWSs are transferred to an online platform from where they are made available.

Commercial microwave links

CML data are acquired either by a network management system (NMS) or by a tailored data acquisition (DAQ) system communicating with network elements through the simple network management protocol (SNMP). Obtaining data from NMS usually does not require the operator to set up a new application, whereas SNMP DAQ needs to be installed on a server connected to the backhaul network and operated and maintained in addition to NMS ([Chwala et al., 2016](#)). Moreover, the secure transfer of data from a backhaul network must not endanger network operations. About half of the OpenSense Action members obtain data through NMS while the remaining half use independently developed SNMP-based DAQ systems.

NMS is a platform used by the operators to monitor network operations and link quality. It includes a set of automated algorithms that adapt the network, in real time, to mitigate

sudden disturbances and degradation in the transmitted signals (Metsälä & Salmelin, 2015). NMS usually provides maxima and minima of RSL and/or TSL every 15-min. Information about the usage of Automatic Transmit Power Control (ATPC) and Adaptive Coding and Modulation (ACM) is sometimes collected by NMS and may help when estimating 15-min total losses from the RSL and TSL extremes. Some NMSs provide either RSL or TSL. If CMLs do not feature ATPC, *i.e.*, they transmit a signal at a constant TSL, RSL data alone enables rainfall retrieval, and vice versa, TSL data alone, in principle, enable rainfall retrieval if the ATPC of CMLs maintains a constant RSL. Finally, rainfall retrieval from RSL alone, in case of variable TSL, is also possible, though with some limitations, provided that some quantitative information about ATPC is available (Roversi *et al.*, 2020).

Specially tailored DAQ systems poll CML data using the SNMP protocol, are located within the closed IP subnetwork of the CMLs and directly connect to the CMLs *via* their IP address. To poll RSL, TSL and other potential data as the outdoor unit temperature, the DAQ system sends a command called an OID (object identifier) *via* an SNMP request to the CMLs. However, the required OIDs for requesting the current RSL and TSL level are not standardised. Different hardware types, even from the same manufacturer, require different OIDs. The correct OIDs have to be identified in the MIB (management information base) file which stores the OIDs for a specific hardware or from manuals where one has to search for specific keywords such as RSL or RX. A small collection of OIDs for different hardware is given in (Chwala *et al.*, 2016). DAQ systems poll instantaneous values of TSL and RSL at a pre-defined sampling frequency. Currently, systems with 1-min sampling (Chwala *et al.*, 2016), or approximately 10 second sampling are used (Andersson *et al.*, 2022; Fencl *et al.*, 2015).

RSL and TSL time series need to be paired with CML metadata: CML id, sublink id, site 0 and site 1 coordinates (locations of antennas), sublink frequencies and, if available, polarizations. Frequency and polarisation affect parameters α and β of attenuation-rainfall relation in Equation (1) and the coordinates uniquely define the position of a CML and its length. Other metadata such as the altitude of the terminals and antenna elevation above ground, or, again, antenna type, may also be available and could help when processing the data.

Several different systems for CML data storage and processing have, so far, been developed and operated for research purposes. A common scheme is the following: RSL and TSL collected by a network operator are provided to an external entity (*e.g.*, a research institution or a national weather service), which is responsible for the rainfall retrieval process. Then the data are paired with metadata and converted to rain intensities using various processing methods (Chwala & Kunstmann, 2019). In this case the CML network operator either provides access to its internal servers to the external organisation or sequentially sends the RSL and TSL data to the external servers in a push command. The data provided by DAQ systems are sent in a raw form or after a basic data quality

check (Andersson *et al.*, 2022). The data-metadata association is done in one of two ways: a) on external servers as part of the rainfall retrieval process using static metadata files updated manually on a regular basis, or b) within a data mediation system run and maintained by the network operator (Andersson *et al.*, 2022). CML data are stored mostly in SQL databases or as text or binary files usually following the format specification of original raw data.

Satellite microwave links

SML data collection and transfer procedures for rain monitoring is divided here into two broad categories:

- A. Satellite receiver terminals (such as DTH TV broadcast receivers, *etc.*) that transmit the data through a different medium other than satellite (*e.g.*, local Internet connection, cellular, *etc.*). As satellite bandwidth is limited, this strategy is flexible with respect to the amount of data stored and transmitted. The majority of SMLs belong to this category.
- B. The satellite ground terminal operates in a two-way fashion: down-link (*i.e.*, TV broadcast from a satellite to the terminal) and up-link (*i.e.*, user-generated traffic plus data about the status of the device, including RSL or SNR), and no other connection apart from the satellite is available. This is the case, for instance, of interactive TV services, or satellite coverage in remote areas for Internet of Things (IoT) connectivity, FinTech and Agritech applications. The raw data are already collected for network management, *i.e.*, only the data that the terminal requires for standard operations are available, such as RSL or SNR.

Procedure B of data collection resembles the CML case where the satellite operator is the owner of the data and can provide it to the potential user. On the other hand, procedure A is somewhat independent of the operator as the received signal at ground can be transferred from the ground receiver to a central server through a terrestrial network which is not usually controlled by the satellite operator.

A typical SML receiver consists of a customary parabolic antenna (*e.g.*, 80-cm diameter) equipped with a universal Low-Noise Block Converter (LNB) which receives the digital TV signals in DVB-S/S2 format, transmitted in Ku-band (10–13 GHz) featuring horizontal or vertical polarisation, from commercial GEO satellites (Giannetti *et al.*, 2022). The LNB outputs a filtered/amplified and down-converted signal in L-band (1–2 GHz) which is sent *via* coaxial cable to a subsequent device for RSL or SNR measurement. Such a device can be either an *ad-hoc* device designed to make these measurements or a customised commercial receiver. In the former, it can be implemented with a low-power IoT electronic board managing data acquisition and transmission functionalities (Colli *et al.*, 2019). In the latter, it consists of a commercial device, suitably modified to make its RSL or SNR measurements available and interfaced with an external router for data logging *via* a terrestrial mobile network (Giannetti *et al.*, 2022).

A highly appealing solution for implementing an SML consists of using a new-generation Eutelsat IoT FIRST (formerly named SmartLNB) commercial receiver (Giannetti *et al.*, 2019). The satellite infrastructure is courtesy of a EUROBIS platform, a bidirectional, satellite-based interactive system owned and operated by Eutelsat. EUROBIS, operating in Ku band and linear polarisation using a Eutelsat 10A satellite in a 10° E orbital position, provides IP-based, transparent communication between the satellite receivers and the Internet. SNR measurements are collected every 30 seconds by the SMLs equipped with Iot FIRST receivers and, subsequently, sent to a fusion centre via the EUROBIS platform through the satellite return link. From there, the user can download the SML data as text files.

RSL (or SNR) time series need to be paired with SML metadata: SML id, site 0 coordinates (*i.e.*, the location of the ground antenna), antenna elevation above ground and antenna altitude above sea level, site 1 (*i.e.*, GEO satellite) latitude and rain height, frequency and polarisation. Other metadata such as digital modulation and error-correcting code format could be helpful as well.

Personal weather stations

A PWS most commonly features a tipping bucket rain gauge which directly measures rain volume by recording bucket tips within some time interval. These outdoor observations are usually transmitted wirelessly to an indoor module over a distance of up to 100 m. The indoor module then transfers the observations to an online platform at a particular set time interval. The rainfall observation always describes the number of tips in the past interval which leads to a delay between the actual time of observation and time of transmission. Another delay is due to data processing and handling by the platform before the output data are available on the server.

The most common format of PWS data is text files (CSV, JSON) with limited metadata information, typically including station IDs, coordinates of the site and, occasionally, the altitude of the site. Temporal resolution of data can differ. For example, from the Netatmo API rainfall observations can be obtained as raw data with irregular timestamps (~5 minutes), processed datasets with homogeneous fixed 5 minutes, hourly or daily intervals. True clarity on how the data are aggregated and processed is lacking.

OS data availability

From the user perspective, the availability of OS data differs significantly for CMLs, SMLs and PWS. CML and SML data is primarily collected by telecommunication network operators to optimize their services and the large majority is not used for OS. In contrast, PWS are intended for atmospheric observations and their owners often share the data with platforms owned by private companies. In many cases, historical PWS data can be accessed online via an API or purchased from the provider (*e.g.*, as was done for the Amsterdam PWS data processed by de Vos (2019b) in the OpenSense sandbox). In

addition, EUMETNET has provided two Europe-wide rainfall data sets from Netamo and WOW platforms for the year 2020 (available [here](#)). For operational purposes, Netatmo offers services to obtain (near) real-time PWS data if a corresponding agreement with the company is signed

CML rainfall retrieval was until recently mostly performed experimentally using data provided to researchers or meteorological services by network operators under nondisclosure agreement and thus accessible only to limited number of researchers. Recently, several CML datasets originally collected by mobile network operators have been published in an open access mode (Andersson *et al.*, 2022; Overeem, 2023) and also data from several dedicated microwave-link experiments are openly available (Špačková *et al.*, 2021; van Leth *et al.*, 2018). Currently, several OpenSense members are involved in pilot projects within which CML data are provided to nongovernmental organizations, mostly meteorological services, in operational mode, nevertheless, details about conditions under which data are provided are confidential.

SML rainfall is retrieved besides researchers also by several consultancy companies who either sell SML-based rainfall products or provide hydrological services based on this data. Access conditions are in this case not publically disclosed. To our knowledge, the only openly accessible SML dataset is that provided by Nefocast project, which is available online and can be freely used for research purposes as long Nefocast project is acknowledged. The data is available in operational mode.

OpenSense members maintain individually several OS datasets, which are now accessible only to individual researchers. OpenSense Action is continuously supporting and coordinating efforts gradually leading to more OS data being published following FAIR principles. OS Datasets arising from OpenSense community plan to follow data format conventions provided in next two sections.

Proposed data and metadata standards

Building from the experience of the OpenSense community, this section provides recommendations for defining common data and metadata standards and formats for CML, PWS, and SML to enable effective rainfall monitoring by OS. We distinguish among required, recommended, and optional variables. The required variables represent the minimal information needed to make use of OS data for rainfall monitoring. Recommended variables are not essential to gather rainfall observation but they improve its accuracy and reliability. Finally, optional variables are currently not used by common processing methods, but they are potentially relevant for improving rainfall monitoring in the future or for monitoring other environmental variables. Sometimes, variables not inherent to the sensor or system of sensors is necessary to derive rainfall information (*e.g.*, rain height by SMLs). We call such variables external and recommend including them in the sensor's dataset.

Commercial microwave links

The CML dataset shall include two main types of data:

1. The metadata table contains a set of parameters characterising the link in terms of its position and other features, such as frequency, polarisation or hardware.
2. The raw data, *i.e.*, the set of dynamic measurements that the CML records such as RSL or TSL.

Raw data are time series, hence they are associated with a timestamp. The metadata table does not have a timestamp but is not static. It can be updated by the cellular operator following changes in the set of operational links. Raw data and metadata are, strictly, all the relevant information for OS of rainfall that can be gathered from the system controlling the network of opportunistic sensors.

Required data

The minimal set of data shall include the following records:

- **(metadata) Location:** The transmitter and receiver coordinates (latitude and longitude) in decimal degrees (°). The location is crucial for determining the path length of the sensor (in km) and the geographical position.
- **(metadata) Link identifier:** A string uniquely identifying a link in a network. It associates time series in the raw data with link features in the metadata.
- **(metadata) Sublink identifier:** a string that identifies the sublink channel.
- **(metadata) Frequency:** The carrier frequency (MHz) is necessary to relate through [Equation \(1\)](#) signal attenuation across the CML path with rainfall intensity.
- **(raw data) Timestamp** (UTC time)
- **(raw data) RSL and/or TSL:** The RSL (in dBm) is the power measurement recorded at the receiver end of the link. The variations in the RSL during a rain event are correlated with the corresponding changes in rainfall intensity.

Even though it is recommended to store both TSL and RSL, in the following two cases just one of these variables used alone enables rainfall retrieval: i) when TSL is maintained as a constant only RSL records are required, ii) when RSL is maintained as a constant, only TSL records alone are required. The latter may not work with moderate to heavy rainfall due to the limited ATPC range usually available. Hence, it is recommended to provide information about an upper limit to which TSL is increased by ATPC.

Recommended data

To gather more accurate rainfall estimates from CMLs, it is also recommended to collect the following data types:

- **(metadata) Signal polarisation.** It is usually either vertical or horizontal.

- **(metadata) Antenna altitude above mean sea level** of each link terminal (m).

Optional data

In addition to RSL and TSL, several other raw data types can be made available by the NMS, such as link failure, ATPC, ACM, sensor temperature, and MIMO information ([Andersson et al., 2022](#); [Roversi et al., 2020](#)). Other potentially useful metadata are hardware characteristics such as antenna dimensions, device manufacturer and model, date of installation, and information about the presence, type and state of protective antenna radomes (whose wetting increases the measured attenuation during rain).

Satellite microwave links

Even though both CML and SML are microwave links, there are important differences between a CML and an SML when it comes to the OS of rainfall. These differences were highlighted in the “opportunistic rainfall sensors” and “current practices in OS data collection” sections and reflect upon different sets of metadata and raw data.

Required data

- **(metadata) Location of the ground receiver and satellite position:** latitude and longitude (in decimal degrees) of the ground receiver, and satellite longitude position (assuming a geostationary orbit). These data determine the elevation angle of the link which is used to determine the length of the slant path through rain.
- **(metadata) Altitude of the ground receiver** (m) above mean sea level.
- **(external data) Rain height** (m): determines the length of the slant path through rain.
- **(metadata) Link identifier:** a string that uniquely identifies a link in a network. It associates time series in raw data with link features in the metadata.
- **(metadata) Sublink identifier:** a string that identifies the sublink channel.
- **(metadata) Frequency** (in MHz)
- **(metadata) Polarisation** (linear V/H in C-, Ku- and Ka-band; circular L/R in C- and Ka-band) of the downlink carrier used for rain attenuation measurements.
- **(raw data) Timestamp** (UTC time)
- **(raw data) RSL (dBm) or SNR (dB):** alternative measurements of the signal strength recorded by the ground receiver.

The rain height information is not an SML-based output. It is, however, in the list of required data as it is mandatory to calculate the length of the propagation path across the liquid precipitation. The rain height can be derived in several ways: i) from the knowledge of the 0°C isotherm height, minus the thickness of the melting layer; ii) from a short-term forecast based on numerical weather prediction models; iii) from

atmospheric profiling; iv) it can be set as a fixed value based on daily or yearly averages *e.g.*, as specified in ITU-R recommendations (ITU-R, 2013), taken at the location of the ground receiver.

Recommended data

- **(metadata) MODCOD** (digital modulation and error-correcting code) format. The combination of modulation and coding determines receiver sensitivity, *i.e.*, the required minimum SNR for proper operation at target error rate. This value expresses the robustness of the receiver to rain fades. The lower the required SNR, the wider the operating range of the receiver as a rain intensity measurement instrument.
- **(metadata) Minimum SNR ratio** (in dB). The required minimum value for SNR which allows proper operation at a target error rate.

Personal weather stations

As PWS are owned and managed at a non-professional level, the data gathered from different stations can largely differ in type, size and quality. Hence, the data that is required for use is limited. Depending on the data source there may be more data relevant for the user which can be added optionally in the data format. The best practice is to follow the recommendations of the Guide to Meteorological Instruments and Methods of Observation edited by the [World Meteorological Organization, \(WMO-No. 8\), Guide to Instruments and Methods of Observation \(2021\)](#).

Required data

- **(metadata) Location:** PWS horizontal coordinates (latitude and longitude) in decimal degrees (°).
- **(metadata) PWS identifier:** an alphanumeric tag that uniquely identifies the station. It associates time series in raw data with sensor features in the metadata.
- **(raw data) Timestamp** (UTC time)
- **(raw data) Rainfall tips/rainfall accumulation.**

The minimal required metadata for a PWS are its coordinates and a unique identifier. Guidelines for the setup and placement of a PWS are provided by the manufacturers but these guidelines may differ from WMO standards and in general, there is no control on how individual stations are set up. As many PWS are installed in built-up areas (cities), it is likely that PWS placement does not follow WMO standards. In the case of Netatmo, an automatic site location and elevation value are generated by the platform when first installing the PWS. If the PWS owner does not manually change this metadata, it may lead to incorrect location attribution. Furthermore, as the elevation metadata can be automatically attributed, it may mean different things, *e.g.*, station height relative to ground, mean sea level, altitude of the site, therefore this value should not be taken at face value.

There may be additional meteorological variables that are being simultaneously measured, *e.g.*, air temperature, wind speed

and direction, relative humidity, air pressure, which can be used for the quality control of rainfall data. It should be noted that if the PWS consists of multiple modules, other meteorological variables are measured by a sensor that may be tens of metres away from the rainfall sensor. Regardless, only one set of location metadata will be given for such a PWS.

For PWS, information on the exact siting of the device can help interpret the data, but it is not a requirement to make use of the data. It is recommended to include any available metadata, with the station location being the only required parameter. Missing data is quite common with the use of PWSs. Thus, it is important to have access to the data in the highest temporal resolution and if observations have been aggregated to larger time steps, to provide information on the calculation choices regarding the number of samples within the time window that may be missed while still generating a rainfall sum over the interval.

Proposed data formats

Most of the OS rainfall data in the literature and the ones available on public online repositories are in either of the two following formats:

- netCDF
- CSV

netCDF is a format developed for creating, accessing, and sharing array-oriented scientific data (UniData, 2021). It is commonly used in meteorology, climatology and hydrology. netCDFs are self-describing and machine-independent, supporting easy data exchange between researchers with different systems and programming languages. In contrast, CSV, being a list of characters separated by commas, is a human-centred format that can be easily understood, but custom data handlers have to be switched in front of the OS software.

NetCDF was chosen as a common data format because it is self-describing, *i.e.* contains all the data and metadata in one file, it is widely used by the climate- and weather-forecast community, and can be interpreted by a wide range of standardised software.

netCDF Format

The netCDF OS data format conventions are maintained on [GitHub](#) and the reader should refer to this repository for the complete up-to-date file structure specifications of the three discussed sensors and for the most recent version of the conventions. This repository also contains examples of files and Python scripts to produce netCDF files according to OS data format conventions. The following text describes the main components of the recommended netCDF structure.

The netCDF file comprises the following components: global attributes, dimensions, coordinate variables, auxiliary coordinate variables, data variables, and external data variables.

- **Global attributes** contain ancillary information describing stored data and should follow the standard structure which is in line with CF conventions

(Hassell *et al.*, 2017). For detailed information one should refer to Table 1 on GitHub ([netCDF_global_attributes.adoc](#)).

- **Dimensions** represent the shape of N-dimensional data variables. Their size is defined either as unlimited (typically by time dimension) or it is an arbitrary positive integer.
- **Coordinate** variables are 1-D variables with the same name as the dimension. They contain the coordinate values of a dimension.
- **Auxiliary coordinate variables** contain coordinate data, but are not coordinate variables in the sense defined above. They do not share a name with dimensions and can be multidimensional. Coordinate variables mostly contain metadata about the sensor, *e.g.*, geographical coordinates, or some sensor characteristics such as frequency for CMLs or type of sensor for PWS.
- **Data variables** are N-dimensional arrays that contain the observations of the sensors (*e.g.* the RSL time series in the case of CMLs)
- **External data variables** contain data from external sources, which are required (or recommended to be used) for data processing

Global attributes common to all three sensors are shown in Table 2. Table 3 shows specifications for CMLs, Table 4 for SMLs, and Table 5 for PWSs. The tables correspond to the OS data format conventions v1.0 maintained at [GitHub](#) The

column named `Attributes` includes properties common to all variables as measurement units (when pertinent) and a string descriptor (`long_name`) as well as properties specific to certain variable types. For a data variable, the `coordinate` attribute is a string containing the auxiliary coordinate variables that belong to the data variable (*e.g.* the rainfall amount coordinate attribute by PWS would be `longitude latitude height_above_ground_level environmental_class hardware`). The `_FillValue` attribute is the conventional value of missing data. It is not set here, but the user should define it. The recommendation is to use, *e.g.*, “NA” or “na”. Coordinate and data variables are classified into required, recommended and optional (fourth column in Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4), as discussed in the section “Proposed data and metadata standards”.

Creating one file with multiple sensors stored along the sensor’s id dimension is recommended only if all sensor data have the same timestamps. In case the timestamps differ, it is recommended to locate each sensor in one netCDF group (supported by netCDF-4) or to create one file for each sensor. The length of the sensor’s id dimension is then equal to 1.

The netCDF file for CML data is split over three dimensions: time period (`time`), CML identifier (`cml_id`), and sublink identifier/s (`sublink_id`). The conventions slightly differ for data obtained by instantaneous and min-max sampling of RSL and TSL. In the first case, data are stored in `rsl` and `tsl` variables and instantaneous sampling is indicated in the `sampling` attribute of the variables, in the second case, `rsl_min`, `rsl_max`, `tsl_min`, and `tsl_max` variables

Table 2. global attributes of netCDF files.

Attribute name	Specification	Requisite
title	brief description of what is inside the dataset	Recommended
file_author(s)	who produced the data and contact	Recommended
institution	where the dataset was produced	Recommended
date	when the dataset was created	Recommended
source	the method of production of the original data. If it is model-generated, the source should include the model and its version. If data are gathered from observations, the source record should characterise it (<i>e.g.</i> , “surface observation” or “radiosonde”)	Recommended
version	version of the dataset (version number or name)	Recommended
history	any modification of the data; the timestamp should be provided for each modification	Recommended
naming convention	the conventional name for OS data is OpenSense-X	Recommended
licence	under which licence the data are available	Recommended
reference	data source or doi, if available. If dataset is merged from multiple independent datasets, provide reference to the original datasets	Optional
comment	diverse information about the dataset (<i>e.g.</i> , precision of coordinates, the time period of the campaign)	Optional

Table 3. CML netCDF specification.

	Type	Attributes	Requisite	Comments
Dimensions				
time				Unlimited size, enforce UTC seconds since 1970-01-01
cml_id				Minim. length is 1
sublink_id				Minim. length is 1
Coordinate variables (dimension)				
time (time)	int/float/double	units = "seconds since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC", long_name = "time_utc", _FillValue	Required	
cml_id (cml_id)	string	long_name = "commercial_microwave_link_identifier"	Required	cml_id has to be unique across the network
sublink_id (sublink_id)	string	long_name = "sublink_identifier"	Required	sublink_id does not have to be unique across the network (but unique within each CML)
Auxiliary coordinate variables (dimension)				
site_0_lat (cml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_0_latitude"	Required	
site_0_lon (cml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_0_longitude"	Required	
site_0_elev (cml_id)	float/double	units = metres_above_sea, long_name = "ground_elevation_above_sea_level_at_site_0"	Optional	
site_0_alt (cml_id)	float/double	units = metres_above_sea, long_name = "antenna_altitude_above_sea_level_at_site_0"	Recommended	
site_1_lat (cml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_1_latitude"	Required	
site_1_lon (cml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_1_longitude"	Required	
site_1_elev (cml_id)	float/double	units = metres_above_sea, long_name = "ground_elevation_above_sea_level_at_site_1"	Optional	
site_1_alt (cml_id)	float/double	units = metres_above_sea, long_name = "antenna_altitude_above_sea_level_at_site_1"	Recommended	
length (cml_id)	float/double	units = m, long_name = "distance_between_pair_of_antennas"	Optional	
frequency (cml_id, sublink_id)	float/double	units = MHz, long_name = "sublink_frequency"	Required	
polarisation (cml_id, sublink_id)	string	units = no units, long_name = "sublink_polarization"	Recommended	When string then 'vertical' or 'horizontal'

	Type	Attributes	Requisite	Comments
Data variables (dimension)				
<i>Specifications for instantaneous sampling (SNMP DAQ)</i>				
tsl (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "transmitted_signal_level", sampling = 'instantaneous', _FillValue	Required*	
rsl (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "received_signal_level", sampling = 'instantaneous', _FillValue	Required*	
<i>Specification for min/max sampling (NMS DAQ)**</i>				
tsl_max (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "maximum_transmitted_signal_level_over_time_window", sampling = 'aggregated', _FillValue	Required*	
tsl_min (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "minimum_transmitted_signal_level_over_time_window", sampling = 'aggregated', _FillValue	Required*	
tsl_avg (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "averaged_transmitted_signal_level_over_time_window", sampling = 'aggregated', _FillValue	Optional	
rsl_max (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "maximum_received_signal_level_over_time_window", sampling = 'aggregated', _FillValue	Required*	
rsl_min (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string with metadata variable_names, long_name = "minimum_received_signal_level_over_time_window", sampling = 'aggregated', _FillValue	Required*	
rsl_avg (cml_id, sublink_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "averaged_received_signal_level_over_time_window", sampling = 'aggregated', _FillValue	Optional	
temperature_0*** (cml_id, time)	float/double	units = degrees_of_celsius, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "sensor_temperature_at_site_0"	Optional	
temperature_1*** (cml_id, time)	float/double	units = degrees_of_celsius, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "sensor_temperature_at_site_1"	Optional	

* It is recommended to store both TSL and RSL, however, when TSL or RSL is maintained as constant, only the variable which is changing is required.

** if other aggregation statistics is used (e.g. mean, median), create a variable rsl_nameOfAggregationStatistics/tsl_nameOfAggregationStatistics and specify details in the global attribute 'comment'

*** Names of variables related to site conditions, such as temperature, should be distinguished by suffixes 0 and 1.

are introduced instead of rsl and tsl and the fact that the values represent statistics over whole observation intervals is indicated in the sampling attribute. If some other statistics than min/max is used to describe observation intervals, a user can define a new variable name, e.g. rsl_avg, or rsl_median and describe the details about this variable in the global attribute comment.

The netCDF file for SML data is split over the following dimensions: time period (time), ground receiver identifier

(receiver_id), satellite identifier (satellite_id), transponder identifier (transponder_id), and sublink identifier (sublink_id).

The netCDF file for PWS data has two dimensions: a timestamp (time) and a PWS identifier (id). Creating one file with multiple PWSs stored along the id dimension is recommended only if PWS data have the same timestamps. For PWSs that start later in the period specified by the time dimension, the first intervals are filled with NA-values. If PWSs

Table 4. SML netCDF specification.

	Type	Attributes	Requisite	Comments
Dimensions				
time				Unlimited size, enforce UTC seconds since 1970-01-01
sml_id				Minimum length is 1
sublink_id				Minimum length is 1
Coordinate variables (dimension)				
time (time)	int/float/double	units = seconds since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC, long_name = "time_utc", _FillValue	Required	
sml_id (sml_id)	string	long_name = "satellite_microwave_link_identifier"	Required	sml_id has to be unique across the link. It includes: receiver_id, satellite_id, trasponder_id
sublink_id (sublink_id)	string	long_name = "sublink_identifier",	Required	sublink_id does not have to be unique across the network (but unique within each SML)
Auxiliary coordinate variables (dimension)				
site_0_lat (sml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_0_latitude"	Required	
site_0_lon (sml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_0_longitude"	Required	
site_0_alt (sml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "antenna_altitude_above_sea_level_at_site_0"	Required	
site_1_lat (sml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_0_latitude"	Optional	0 degrees
site_1_lon (sml_id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84_projection, long_name = "site_1_longitude"	Required	
site_1_alt (sml_id)	float/double	units = metres_above_sea, long_name = "ground_elevation_above_sea_level_at_site_1"	Optional	36,000 km
frequency (sml_id, sublink_id)	float/double	units = MHz, long_name = "sublink_frequency"	Required	
polarisation (sml_id, sublink_id)	string	units = no units, long_name = "sublink_polarization"	Required	When string then 'vertical' or 'horizontal'
Data variables (dimension)				
snr (sml_id, time)	float/double	units = dB, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "signal_to_noise_ratio", _FillValue	Required*	
rsl (sml_id, time)	float/double	units = dBm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names, long_name = "received_signal_level", _FillValue	Required*	
modcod (sml_id, time)	string	long_name = "modcod_format"	Optional	
External data variables (dimension)				
rain_height (time, sml_id)	float/double	units = m, long_name = "length_of_the_slant_path_through_the_rain"	Required	

* It is required to store either snr or rsl.

Table 5. PWS netCDF specification.

	Type	Attributes	Requisite	Comments
Dimensions				
time				Unlimited size, enforce UTC seconds since 1970-01-01
id				
Coordinate variables (dimension)				
time (time)	int/float/double	units = seconds since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC, long_name = "time_utc", _FillValue	Required	Timestamp refers to the end of observation interval
id (id)	string	long_name = "personal_weather_station_identifier"	Required	id has to be unique across the network
Auxiliary coordinate variables (dimension)				
lat (id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84 projection, long_name = "latitude"	Required	
lon (id)	float/double	units = degrees_in_WGS84 projection, long_name = "longitude"	Required	
elev (id)	float/double	units = metres_above_sea, long_name = "ground_elevation_above_sea_level"	Recommended	
Height_above ground_level (id)	float/double	units = metres	Recommended	
Environmental_class (id)	integer	no unit	Recommended	
hardware (id)	string	long_name = "manufactuer_and_model_type"	Optional	e.g. manufacturer, station type, sensor types
Data variables (dimension)				
rainfall_amount (id, time)	float/double	long_name = "rainfall_amount_per_time_unit", units = mm, coordinates = string_with_auxiliary_coordinate_variable_names	Required	
Optional data (dimension)				
temperature (id, time)	float/double	units = degrees_celsius	Optional	
relative_humidity (id, time)	float/double	units = %	Optional	
wind_velocity (id, time)	float/double	units = ms-1	Optional	
wind_direction (id, time)	float/double	units = degrees	Optional	
air_pressure (id, time)	float/double	units = hPa	Optional	

timestamps differ, it is recommended to store each PWS in a netCDF group (supported by netCDF-4) or to create a file for each PWS. If the optional data consisting of additional meteorological variables have a different timestamp, it is recommended to interpolate these variables at the timestamps of the rainfall data to have a structured, fixed time series.

When merging multiple datasets we recommend referring to original datasets in a netCDF global attribute *reference*. Possible overlapping of sensors should be checked using metadata about positions of sensors, however, as colocation of opportunistic sensors is rather common (e.g. in case of CMLs of two independent operators) we recommend to remove

duplicates only if one is sure beyond a reasonable doubt that collocated sensors are from exact the same data source. Furthermore, as uniqueness of sensor's identifiers is not ensured within independent datasets, new ids might be required. Unless there are specific reasons to choose otherwise, we suggest constructing new ids, *e.g.* using prefixes, such as they enable user to distinguish between original data sources. ID taxonomy should be described in a netCDF global attribute `comment`.

CSV Format

The proposal is to follow naming conventions and units defined in netCDF but not to enforce any other requirements on the structure. A header of the table should be present. As in the netCDF files, the format of the missing value names is not set, but it should be defined. The recommendation is to use *e.g.*, "NA" or "na". It is also highly recommended to include a Readme file with a description of general information concerning the data, as covered in the global attributes of netCDF files (*i.e.*, title, author/s, institution, date, *etc.*).

Commercial microwave links

The proposal is to follow the naming conventions defined for netCDF as much as possible (see section "netCDF format"), but not to enforce any other requirements on the structure. The character of the CSV files does not allow for any direct inclusion of metadata of individual sensors. Therefore, a metadata table is needed for the storage of information covered in the data coordinates of the netCDF files (*e.g.*, coordinates of sites, CML length, frequency, polarisation, *etc.*), preferably with the same naming convention. Another table should store the time series of the CML variable observations.

Satellite microwave links

The recommendations concerning naming and metadata are similar to those for CML. As for storing the data collected by a network of SML sensors, we recommend following the approach described in [F. Giannetti et al. \(2019\)](#) where each sensor produces its own CSV file.

Personal weather stations

If PWS data are provided in CSV form, the data should be divided over two tables with the first consisting of the data where each column represents the time series of a single PWS. The first column of the table is to indicate the timestamps of the end of the interval. This CSV format anticipates some pre-processing of rainfall observations to fixed time intervals. In the case of multiple observations within a time interval, the rainfall amounts are added. If no observation is reported in the fixed time interval, the value in the table for that timestamp becomes NA. In another CSV table, metadata are provided for each PWS. Each row corresponds with the PWS id, provided in the first column, followed by columns of the respective longitude, latitude, elevation (if possible) and any other metadata related to that PWS that may be available, including information about the originator of the data (*e.g.*, name, contact number, *etc.*).

The CSV format does not allow for overarching metadata as the netCDF format does. A good example of a structure of

PWS data and metadata in the CSV format is the Amsterdam PWS dataset by [de Vos \(2019b\)](#). This dataset is also available in the [OpenSense SANDBOX](#).

Conclusions and outlook on OS data application

This paper presents the current practices of collecting and storing precipitation OS data and corresponding metadata. For the first time, we introduce common guidelines defining i) requirements on data and metadata collected from CMLs, SMLs, and PWSs, ii) conventions for naming collected variables and different parameters of metadata, and iii) specifications on data format used for storing the data and metadata in files. These guidelines will enable storing OS datasets in a standardised form, thus easing their processing, sharing, and integration. Common naming conventions will facilitate communication of OS research and its applications. Specifications defining recommended and required data and metadata will improve the reliability of OS datasets and their quality control. The OS format conventions are maintained at [GitHub repository](#) of OpenSense Action and the reader is referred there for the most recent version.

Until recently, OS datasets were mostly maintained by individual research groups or meteorological services. Fortunately, there is an increasing number of datasets which has been published in open access mode and OpenSense strive to make more OS data FAIR, first under access requiring authentication, and gradually also in an open access mode. Furthermore, OpenSense members are involved in several pilot projects within which PWS and CML data are provided to nongovernmental organizations in operational mode. Data interoperability is a key issue when upscaling local and regional OS observation systems and curating gradually increasing datasets and will become even more pronounced in the near future with a new generation of 5G/6G networks integrating communication with sensing (ISAC). In this respect standardization of data formats complying with the needs of end-users, currently mostly European NHMSs and their umbrella organization EUMETNET, is one piece of the puzzle making it easier for data owners to offer sensing as a service.

The definition of common netCDF specifications represents an important step towards automated processing of OS raw data and community development of joint OS software packages. netCDF is a self-describing machine-readable binary format enabling the efficient handling of potentially large datasets at different platforms. The OpenSense community is currently collaborating on collecting OS software packages which have been developed by individual researchers and on harmonising their usage within a shared [SANDBOX environment](#). A common definition of data formats is crucial for the future interoperability of developed software and automated processing of OS data collected. We also recommended how to store data and metadata in human-readable CSV files as it is a format which most users can read and is a widely used data format in open science. With the definition of CSV files, we do not aim for a unique specification of the data structure, but to give general recommendations which will later ease the conversion of these files to uniquely defined netCDF files.

These guidelines arose from a bottom-up effort of OS researchers and OS end users associated in the OpenSense Action. The guidelines will simplify the uptake of opportunistic sensors as a relevant source of rainfall observations which can complement existing standard monitoring systems and improve our understanding of Earth's water cycle. They should also make easier to OS data owners to provide their data in a format that suits the end user.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

References

- Ahrens CD: **Meteorology Today: An Introduction to Weather, Climate, and the Environment**, 10th edition. ed. Brooks Cole, Belmont, CA, 2012.
[Reference Source](#)
- Andersson JCM, Olsson J, van de Beek R, et al.: **OpenMRG: Open data from Microwave links, Radar, and Gauges for rainfall quantification in Gothenburg, Sweden**. *Earth System Science Data*. 2022; **14**: 5411–5426.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bárdossy A, Seidel J, El Hachem A: **The use of personal weather station observations to improve precipitation estimation and interpolation**. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sci*. 2021; **25**: 583–601.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Brenot H, Neméghaire J, Delobbe L, et al.: **Preliminary signs of the initiation of deep convection by GNSS**. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*. 2013; **13**: 5425–5449.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chwala C, Keis F, Kunstmann H: **Real-time data acquisition of commercial microwave link networks for hydrometeorological applications**. *Atmos Meas Tech*. 2016; **9**: 991–999.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chwala C, Kunstmann H: **Commercial microwave link networks for rainfall observation: Assessment of the current status and future challenges**. *WIREs Water*. 2019; **6**: e1337.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Colli M, Cassola F, Martina F, et al.: **Rainfall Fields Monitoring Based on Satellite Microwave Down-Links and Traditional Techniques in the City of Genoa**. *IEEE Trans Geosci Remote Sens*. 2020; **58**: 6266–6280.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Colli M, Stagnaro M, Caridi A, et al.: **A Field Assessment of a Rain Estimation System Based on Satellite-to-Earth Microwave Links**. *IEEE Trans Geosci Remote Sens*. 2019; **57**: 2864–2875.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- David N, Sendik O, Messer H, et al.: **Cellular Network Infrastructure: The Future of Fog Monitoring?** *Bull Am Meteorol Soc*. 2015; **96**(10): 1687–1698.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- de Vos LW, Leijnse H, Overeem A, et al.: **The potential of urban rainfall monitoring with crowdsourced automatic weather stations in Amsterdam**. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sci*. 2017; **21**: 765–777.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- de Vos LW, Leijnse H, Overeem A, et al.: **Quality Control for Crowdsourced Personal Weather Stations to Enable Operational Rainfall Monitoring**. *Geophys Res Lett*. 2019a; **46**: 8820–8829.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- de Vos LW: **Rainfall observations datasets from Personal Weather Stations**. 2019b.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Dong R, Liao J, Li B, et al.: **Measurements of rainfall rates from videos**. In: *2017 10th International Congress on Image and Signal Processing, BioMedical Engineering and Informatics (CISP-BMEI)*. Presented at the 2017 10th International Congress on Image and Signal Processing, BioMedical Engineering and Informatics (CISP-BMEI). 2017.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Douša J, Dick G, Kacmarik M, et al.: **Benchmark campaign and case study episode in central Europe for development and assessment of advanced GNSS tropospheric models and products**. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*. 2016; **9**: 2989–3008.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- ECC: **ECC Report 173 - Fixed Service in Europe Current use and future trends post 2016**. 2012.
[Reference Source](#)
- Elgered G: **An overview of COST Action 716: exploitation of ground-based GPS for climate and numerical weather prediction applications**. *Phys Chem Earth*. Proceedings of the First COST Action 716 Workshop Towards Operational GPS Meteorology and the Second Network Workshop of the International GPS Service (IGS). 2001; **26**: 399–404.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ericsson: **Ericsson Microwave Outlook Report - 2023**. 2023.
[Reference Source](#)
- Ernst & Young - Parthenon: **Satellite internet: The next big wave - Market study report**. 2023.
[Reference Source](#)
- Fencel M, Dohnal M, Bareš V: **Retrieving Water Vapor From an E-Band Microwave Link With an Empirical Model Not Requiring In Situ Calibration**. *Earth Space Sci*. 2021; **8**(11): e2021EA001911.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fencel M, Rieckermann J, Šykora P, et al.: **Commercial microwave links instead of rain gauges: fiction or reality?** *Water Sci Technol*. 2015; **71**(1): 31–37.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Giannetti F, Moretti M, Reggiani R, et al.: **The NEFOCAST System for Detection and Estimation of Rainfall Fields by the Opportunistic Use of Broadcast Satellite Signals**. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*. 2019; **34**: 16–27.
[Reference Source](#)
- Giannetti F, Reggiani R: **Opportunistic Rain Rate Estimation from Measurements of Satellite Downlink Attenuation: A Survey**. *Sensors (Basel)*. 2021; **21**(7): 5872.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Giannetti F, Vaccaro A, Sapienza F, et al.: **Multi-Satellite Rain Sensing: Design Criteria and Implementation Issues**. In: *2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC)*. Presented at the 2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC). 2022; 1–4.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Graf M, Chwala C, Polz J, et al.: **Rainfall estimation from a German-wide commercial microwave link network: Optimized processing and validation for one year of data**. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sci*. 2019; 1–23.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Guerova G, Jones J, Douša J, et al.: **Review of the state of the art and future prospects of the ground-based GNSS meteorology in Europe**. *Atmos Meas Tech*. 2016; **9**(11): 5385–5406.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hassell D, Gregory J, Blower J, et al.: **A data model of the Climate and Forecast metadata conventions (CF-1.6) with a software implementation (cf-python v2; 1)**. *Geosci Model Dev*. 2017; **10**(12): 4619–4646.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- ITU-R: **Report ITU-R F.2323-1, Fixed service use and future trends (No. F.2323-1)**. International Telecommunication Union. 2017.
[Reference Source](#)
- ITU-R: **RECOMMENDATION ITU-R P.839-4 - Rain height model for prediction methods**. 2013.
[Reference Source](#)
- ITU-R: **RECOMMENDATION ITU-R P.838-3, Specific attenuation model for rain for use in prediction methods**. 2005.
[Reference Source](#)
- Jones J, Guerova G, Douša J, et al.: **Advanced GNSS Tropospheric Products for**

Monitoring Severe Weather Events and Climate: COST Action ES1206 Final Action Dissemination Report. Springer International Publishing, Cham. 2020.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Li H, Wang X, Wu S, *et al.*: **An Improved Model for Detecting Heavy Precipitation Using GNSS-Derived Zenith Total Delay Measurements.** *IEEE J Sel Top Appl Earth Obs Remote Sens.* 2021; **14**: 5392–5405.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Liu F, Cui Y, Masouros C, *et al.*: **Integrated sensing and communications: Toward dual-functional wireless networks for 6G and beyond.** *IEEE J Sel Areas Commun.* 2022; **40**(6): 1728–67.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Lorenz C, Kunstmann H: **The Hydrological Cycle in Three State-of-the-Art Reanalyses: Intercomparison and Performance Analysis.** *J Hydrometeor.* 2012; **13**: 1397–1420.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Metsälä EM, Salmelin JTT: **LTE Backhaul: Planning and Optimization.** John Wiley & Sons, 2015.
[Reference Source](#)

Muller CL, Chapman L, Johnston S, *et al.*: **Crowdsourcing for climate and atmospheric sciences: current status and future potential.** *Int J Climatol.* 2015; **35**(11): 3185–3203.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ochoa-Rodriguez S, Wang LP, Gires A, *et al.*: **Impact of spatial and temporal resolution of rainfall inputs on urban hydrodynamic modelling outputs: A multi-catchment investigation.** *J Hydrol (Amst).* Hydrologic Applications of Weather Radar, 2015; **531**: 389–407.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Olsen R, Rogers D, Hodge D: **The aR² relation in the calculation of rain attenuation.** *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation.* 1978; **26**(2): 318–329.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ostrometzky J, Cherkassky D, Messer H: **Accumulated Mixed Precipitation Estimation Using Measurements from Multiple Microwave Links.** *Adv Meteorol.* 2015; **2015**(2): e707646.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Overeem A: **Commercial microwave link data for rainfall monitoring.** 2023.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Overeem A, Leijnse H, Uijlenhoet R: **Country-wide rainfall maps from cellular communication networks.** *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2013; **110**(8): 2741–2745.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Roversi G, Alberoni PP, Fornasiero A, *et al.*: **Commercial microwave links as a tool for operational rainfall monitoring in Northern Italy.** *Atmos Meas Tech.* 2020; **13**(11): 5779–5797.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Rubin Y, Rostkier-Edelstein D, Chwala C, *et al.*: **Challenges in Diurnal Humidity Analysis from Cellular Microwave Links (CML) over Germany.** *Remote Sens.* 2022; **14**(10): 2353.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Špačková A, Bareš V, Fencel M, *et al.*: **A year of attenuation data from a commercial dual-polarized duplex microwave link with concurrent disdrometer, rain gauge, and weather observations.** *Earth Syst Sci Data.* 2021; **13**(8): 4219–4240.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Tauro F, Selker J, van de Giesen N, *et al.*: **Measurements and Observations in the XXI century (MOXXI): innovation and multi-disciplinarity to sense the hydrological cycle.** *Hydrol Sci J.* 2018; **63**(2): 169–196.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

UniData: **NetCDF Users Guide: The NetCDF User's Guide.** [WWW Document], 2021. (accessed 11.22.22).
[Reference Source](#)

van Leth TC, Overeem A, Uijlenhoet R, *et al.*: **Wageningen Urban Rainfall experiment.** 2018.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

WMO: **Guide to Instruments and Methods of Observation (WMO-No. 8).** 2018th and 2021 editions ed WMO., WMO, Geneva. 2021.
[Reference Source](#)

Zhao Q, Yao Y, Yao W, *et al.*: **Real-time precise point positioning-based zenith tropospheric delay for precipitation forecasting.** *Sci Rep.* 2018; **8**(1): 7939.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Zheng F, Tao R, Maier HR, *et al.*: **Crowdsourcing Methods for Data Collection in Geophysics: State of the Art, Issues, and Future Directions.** *Rev Geophys.* 2018; **56**(4): 698–740.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 2

Reviewer Report 22 February 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18616.r38145>

© 2024 Chakraborty S. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Swastika Chakraborty

Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, Narula Institute of Technology, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

The revisions are appropriate. I have read the article. They are sufficient for me.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Satellite Communication, Climate Studies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 16 November 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.17348.r36009>

© 2023 Chakraborty S. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Swastika Chakraborty

Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, Narula Institute of Technology, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

The article addresses a very important issue about rainfall ground truth information collection through opportunistic sensor and dissemination of it. The common data format as proposed here

(.csv and NETCDF) is necessary. According to me for the maximum coverage of spatio-temporal information the collection process should not be limited to continental boundary, neither it is limited to government organization. To my knowledge CML is maintained mostly by private organizations for their purpose. They are not for preserving continuous data. Therefore, some policy is needed to encourage private operator for the purpose to participate to the network. CCTV is an important, economic device, only it needs a proper policy guideline to use the existing network across the globe.

An international controlling forum like ITU is required to be formed to avoid redundancy of data collection and to make aware the user about the data usage policy. The three types of data that described here i.e. required data, redundant data and optional data are enough for the purpose of rainfall research. However, collection of the data of instruments like RADAR of different type, Laser Precipitation Monitor, Disdrometer, Radiometer may add value for the purpose.

Data storage policy and data charging policy for procurement needs to be proposed.

Major Comments:

1. Insert separate paragraphs looking at user's requirement, i.e. what are the steps to be performed to use the data, how the data to be acknowledged, how the charging process to be satisfied.
2. It is better to include a flow diagram for the data user.
3. More types of sensors as discussed are to be included.
4. Discuss significance of data resolution on the application in a paragraph

Minor Comments:

Include section and sub section numbering.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Yes

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to

implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Satellite Communication, Climate Studies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 29 Jan 2024

Martin FencI

Response to the comments *We thank both reviewers and one reader, Pinhas Alpert, for their valuable comments. We respond to the comments at respective places in the text below. Both reviews are raising questions related to availability of opportunistic sensing (OS) data. While OS data availability is intentionally not at the center of our paper, which focuses on OS data standards and formats, we understand that it is a crucial aspect for a reader (potential end user) who does not yet have access to OS data. Thus, we address the issue of OS data availability in more detail in the introducing sections of the revised version of the manuscript.* **Reviewer**

Report II Approved with Reservations Swastika Chakraborty, Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, Narula Institute of Technology, Kolkata, West Bengal, India The article addresses a very important issue about rainfall ground truth information collection through opportunistic sensor and dissemination of it. The common data format as proposed here (.csv and NETCDF) is necessary. According to me for the maximum coverage of spatio-temporal information the collection process should not be limited to continental boundary, neither it is limited to government organization. To my knowledge CML is maintained mostly by private organizations for their purpose. They are not for preserving continuous data. Therefore, some policy is needed to encourage private operator for the purpose to participate to the network. CCTV is an important, economic device, only it needs a proper policy guideline to use the existing network across the globe. An international controlling forum like ITU is required to be formed to avoid redundancy of data collection and to make aware the user about the data usage policy. The three types of data that described here i.e. required data, redundant data and optional data are enough for the purpose of rainfall research. However, collection of the data of instruments like RADAR of different type, Laser Precipitation Monitor, Disdrometer, Radiometer may add value for the purpose.

Data storage policy and data charging policy for procurement needs to be proposed.

We thank the reviewer for all the comments. While we acknowledge the importance of new topics raised by the reviewer, we intend to have our paper focused primarily on new data format conventions for three selected opportunistic sensors. We also review data collection practices, nevertheless again with the focus on three selected sensors and with the focus on the technical aspects of the data acquisition. The paper arises from the experience of OpenSense network, which tackles the challenge of OS data availability and accessibility at different levels. OpenSense network involves now about eight European national meteorological services and their

organization EUMETNET, many OS researchers, but also several providers of OS data. Common data format conventions, discussed in this paper, are considered by the members of the network as a major step towards improving OS data interoperability and thus represents a significant contribution towards a global uptake of OS data and its integration into standard weather observation networks. Major Comments:

1. Insert separate paragraphs looking at user's requirement, i.e. what are the steps to be performed to use the data, how the data to be acknowledged, how the charging process to be satisfied.

We partly address the user perspective in a new data availability section. In here, we describe how one can obtain historical open access data from CMLs and discuss also the possibility to buy data from data-collection platforms operated by PWS manufacturers. In the case of CMLs, negotiations between several met offices and mobile network operators to get CML data operationally are now in process, nevertheless, details are confidential. Regarding SMLs, there are few private companies collecting this data on their own and providing services based on this data. Business models for monetizing OS data including charging strategies are not in the hands of OpenSense members, but in the hands of data owners and we do not have information to reliably comment on it. Moreover, we think this issue would be beyond the scope of this paper. On the other hand, we are convinced, that suggested data formats might ease upscaling of OS data business, as they improve data interoperability and make easier for end users to use software tools being currently developed within OpenSense community. In the revised manuscript, this is now stressed more in the concluding section. Regarding processing of OS data ('the steps to be performed to use the data'), a reader is referred to literature provided in the introduction.

1. It is better to include a flow diagram for the data user.

As explained above, the authors of this manuscript are not in the position to propose a technical solution, how data is/will be delivered to end users.

1. More types of sensors as discussed are to be included.

The OpenSense community can act as a reference group for usage of data from three OS sensors discussed in this paper (CMLs, SMLs, and PWSs). Thus, we do not plan to include for now other sensors into our standards. That said, we are aware that that the field of OS is dynamically evolving and other sensors might become commonly used in future. Data format conventions maintained on [GitHub](#) presented in this paper will hopefully contribute also to the other future OS data standardization efforts. For traditional sensors, mentioned in the general comment, CF conventions provide widely accepted data format standards.

1. Discuss significance of data resolution on the application in a paragraph

Data resolution is mentioned in the new paragraph estimating number of sensors worldwide, in addition common data resolution of different sensors is provided in Table 1. To keep the conclusion focused on the subject of this paper, i.e. new data format conventions, we prefer to keep information about typical temporal resolution of discussed OS sensors in the introducing section. Minor Comments:

Include section and sub section numbering. Section numbers have been removed by the handling editor as it does not comply with ORE style.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 23 October 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.17348.r35561>

© 2023 Lussana C. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Cristian Lussana

The Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Oslo, Norway

The authors represent the OpenSense community, which comprises researchers and professionals primarily engaged in the public sector, including governmental institutions and universities, among others. In their paper, the authors share valuable insights into the use of opportunistic sensors for precipitation measurement. I appreciate that the authors provide concise summaries of the three data sources discussed in the paper: CML, SML, and PWS. The paper's central focus lies in recommendations regarding the typical file structure necessary for data storage. I concur with the authors' fundamental idea that adopting a common format can facilitate data sharing among OpenSense members and potentially extend to the broader scientific community. The suggested formats, both netCDF and CSV file formats, seem reasonable and well-suited for this purpose.

However, a limitation of this paper is that it does not delve into the interaction between private companies providing the data, a scenario that frequently occurs, and the public institutions that utilize them. As a reader, I am left wondering if the proposed recommendations hold value for data providers. Do they perceive the benefits of organizing data according to the proposed structure? Moreover, with an increasing number of potential users, would this make a significant difference for them?

In this regard, I believe that the paper would become more engaging if the authors included a paragraph in the introduction addressing these questions.

In conclusion, I find this manuscript to be a valuable contribution to the ongoing discussion on how to maximize the utility of opportunistic observations. I recommend its indexing after the authors have addressed the following comments.

Comments:

1. Introduction (Page 4): The statement, "The number of opportunistic sensors has already exceeded the number of conventional instruments by an order of magnitude and is still increasing," is the only place in the manuscript where the authors explicitly mention that opportunistic measurements yield a substantial volume of data. Personally, I believe that redundancy is a key characteristic of this type of data. It would enhance the paper's appeal to readers if the authors provided a broader characterization of the available data, at least on a continental level, based on their extensive experience. Perhaps you could include a paragraph estimating the potential number of observations available for each time step and data source, offering a broad range (e.g., PWS from 10,000 to 100,000 every hour) based on the SANDBOX environment mentioned on Page 17 in your conclusions.

2. I anticipate that many readers might begin reading the paper with questions like, "How can I obtain this data?" However, the authors do not answer this question explicitly, as they make it clear from the beginning that their focus is on addressing questions such as, "Once you have the data, we propose organizing them in this manner..." To assist users, it might be helpful if you included additional references from your work within the OpenSense community that describe the process of obtaining the data as comprehensively as possible.
3. It is evident that the authors embrace a bottom-up approach, wherein individual researchers can benefit from interactions with others seeking to address similar data-related issues. Nevertheless, this approach has limitations, particularly in the identification of unique identifiers for PWS and Link Identifiers for CML and SML. What happens when different datasets are merged? Is there a way to prevent two different research groups from using the same identifier for two different PWSs, for instance? Do you have any suggestions for avoiding such situations?

Minor comments:

Plain language summary, 1st line: Adjust the statement that includes "devices primarily intended not intended."

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Yes

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Meteorology, climatology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of

expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Author Response 29 Jan 2024

Martin FencI

Response to the comments *We thank both reviewers and one reader, Pinhas Alpert, for their valuable comments. We respond to the comments at respective places in the text below. Both reviews are raising questions related to availability of opportunistic sensing (OS) data. While OS data availability is intentionally not at the center of our paper, which focuses on OS data standards and formats, we understand that it is a crucial aspect for a reader (potential end user) who does not yet have access to OS data. Thus, we address the issue of OS data availability in more detail in the introducing sections of the revised version of the manuscript.* **Reviewer Report I Approved** Cristian Lussana, The Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Oslo, Norway
The authors represent the OpenSense community, which comprises researchers and professionals primarily engaged in the public sector, including governmental institutions and universities, among others. In their paper, the authors share valuable insights into the use of opportunistic sensors for precipitation measurement. I appreciate that the authors provide concise summaries of the three data sources discussed in the paper: CML, SML, and PWS. The paper's central focus lies in recommendations regarding the typical file structure necessary for data storage. I concur with the authors' fundamental idea that adopting a common format can facilitate data sharing among OpenSense members and potentially extend to the broader scientific community. The suggested formats, both netCDF and CSV file formats, seem reasonable and well-suited for this purpose.

However, a limitation of this paper is that it does not delve into the interaction between private companies providing the data, a scenario that frequently occurs, and the public institutions that utilize them. As a reader, I am left wondering if the proposed recommendations hold value for data providers. Do they perceive the benefits of organizing data according to the proposed structure? Moreover, with an increasing number of potential users, would this make a significant difference for them?

In this regard, I believe that the paper would become more engaging if the authors included a paragraph in the introduction addressing these questions.

In conclusion, I find this manuscript to be a valuable contribution to the ongoing discussion on how to maximize the utility of opportunistic observations. I recommend its indexing after the authors have addressed the following comments. *We are pleased to read that our central idea of common data standards and formats is considered valuable. Suggested OS data format recommendations evolved indeed from a bottom-up approach following the needs of OS researchers and OS data end users. We see the common data format as one important piece of the puzzle enabling the adoption of OS observations by a wide range of end users and in this sense also as an opportunity for data owners to monetize data they anyway have. Interoperability is a key issue when upscaling precipitation monitoring with opportunistic sensors. In this respect, standardization of data formats complying with the needs of end users plays an important role. The suggested standards evolve from OPENSENSE community having members from most of the European countries and involving eight European NHMSs and their umbrella organization EUMETNET. We are convinced OPENSENSE is able to create a critical mass required for wider*

acknowledgement of these standards. Designing data standards is not an isolated activity. It is part of a broader effort to boost an uptake of opportunistic sensors by relevant stakeholders in meteorology and hydrometeorology and motivate data owners to provide data for OS of precipitation and/or other atmospheric variables. ... Do they perceive the benefits of organizing data according to the proposed structure? Moreover, with an increasing number of potential users, would this make a significant difference for them? ... We now partly address the potential of these data format conventions for the data owners in section in the conclusions but, at the same time, we stress there that a new format is bottom-up effort mainly initiated by OS researchers and end users associated in OpenSense network. As the OpenSense network we try reach OS data owners also at different levels, nevertheless, these efforts are out of the scope of this paper.

Comments:

1. Introduction (Page 4): The statement, "The number of opportunistic sensors has already exceeded the number of conventional instruments by an order of magnitude and is still increasing," is the only place in the manuscript where the authors explicitly mention that opportunistic measurements yield a substantial volume of data. Personally, I believe that redundancy is a key characteristic of this type of data. It would enhance the paper's appeal to readers if the authors provided a broader characterization of the available data, at least on a continental level, based on their extensive experience. Perhaps you could include a paragraph estimating the potential number of observations available for each time step and data source, offering a broad range (e.g., PWS from 10,000 to 100,000 every hour) based on the SANDBOX environment mentioned on Page 17 in your conclusions.

Agreed. We have added a paragraph to Introduction estimating potential number of observations worldwide available from OS. The availability of OS data is discussed in a new subsection OS data availability.

1. I anticipate that many readers might begin reading the paper with questions like, "How can I obtain this data?" However, the authors do not answer this question explicitly, as they make it clear from the beginning that their focus is on addressing questions such as, "Once you have the data, we propose organizing them in this manner..." To assist users, it might be helpful if you included additional references from your work within the OpenSense community that describe the process of obtaining the data as comprehensively as possible.

We address this question in the revised manuscript in a new subsection called OS data availability. Here we refer to openly available datasets and describe some community efforts facilitating publishing of further datasets. We have also added one paragraph about data availability in the conclusions.

1. It is evident that the authors embrace a bottom-up approach, wherein individual researchers can benefit from interactions with others seeking to address similar data-related issues. Nevertheless, this approach has limitations, particularly in the identification of unique identifiers for PWS and Link Identifiers for CML and SML. What happens when different datasets are merged? Is there a way to prevent two different research groups from using the same identifier for two different PWSs, for instance? Do you have any suggestions for avoiding such situations?

Thank you for pointing this out. Indeed, as a community driven by researchers we have to rely on bottom-up approach with all the limitations it brings. We cannot ensure uniqueness of identifiers globally, but they have to be unique within one dataset. We, nevertheless, agree that

nonuniqueness of identifiers might be an issue when merging two datasets. We thus added in section Proposed data and metadata standards recommendations on merging independent datasets:

- *We propose to mention original datasets in global attribute reference.*
- *We recommend checking possible overlapping using metadata about positions of sensors, however, we recommend to remove duplicates only if one is sure beyond a reasonable doubt that collocated sensors are the exact same data source as collocated observations (e.g. CMLs of different operators) are more common by opportunistic sensors than it is usual in traditional observational networks*
- *Unless there are specific reasons to choose otherwise, we suggest constructing new IDs, e.g. using prefixes, such as they enable user to distinguish between original data sources.*
- *We suggest describing ID taxonomy in a netCDF global attribute comment*

Minor comments:

Plain language summary, 1st line: Adjust the statement that includes "devices primarily intended not intended." *Corrected.*

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Comments on this article

Version 1

Author Response 29 Jan 2024

Martin Fencel

We would like to thank the reader for reading our manuscript and taking time to suggest improvements. Our responses are below the comments.

Reader's Comment PINHAS ALPERT, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Israel This paper deals with an important topic of data standardization for opportunistic sensors. All in all this paper is well written, clear, and comes in a timely manner. However, I would like to raise a short comment regarding some important missing references. First, please consider adding the following reference which gives a clear and detailed overview of the available CML data-collection systems:

H. Messer and O. Sendik, "A New Approach to Precipitation Monitoring: A critical survey of existing technologies and challenges," in *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 110-122, May 2015, doi: 10.1109/MSP.2014.2309705

*Thank you for this recommendation. We have at the end decided to refer to more recent review paper about this topic. Chwala, Christian, and Harald Kunstmann. "Commercial Microwave Link Networks for Rainfall Observation: Assessment of the Current Status and Future Challenges." *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water* 6, no. 2 (2019): e1337. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1337>. Second, another important point is that opportunistic sensors use is not limited to rainfall. E.g., humidity can be monitored*

using CMLs [1], as well as other types of phenomena such as fog [2] and different types of precipitation (snow, sleet) [3]. These further capabilities might be worthwhile to mention in the background.

[1] Rubin Y, Rostkier-Edelstein D, Chwala C, Alpert P. Challenges in Diurnal Humidity Analysis from Cellular Microwave Links (CML) over Germany. *Remote Sensing*. 2022; 14(10):2353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14102353>

[2] David, N., O. Sendik, H. Messer, and P. Alpert, 2015: Cellular Network Infrastructure: The Future of Fog Monitoring?. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 96, 1687–1698,

<https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-13-00292.1> [3] Jonatan Ostrometzky, Dani Cherkassky, Hagit Messer, "Accumulated Mixed Precipitation Estimation Using Measurements from Multiple Microwave Links", *Advances in Meteorology*, vol. 2015, Article ID 707646, 9 pages, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/707646> Thank you, we have added this information together with the references into the section describing principle of CML rainfall estimation.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reader Comment 13 Nov 2023

PINHAS ALPERT, Geophysics, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Israel

This paper deals with an important topic of data standardization for opportunistic sensors. All in all this paper is well written, clear, and comes in a timely manner. However, I would like to raise a short comment regarding some important missing references.

First, please consider adding the following reference which gives a clear and detailed overview of the available CML data-collection systems:

H. Messer and O. Sendik, "A New Approach to Precipitation Monitoring: A critical survey of existing technologies and challenges," in *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 110-122, May 2015, doi: 10.1109/MSP.2014.2309705

Second, another important point is that opportunistic sensors use is not limited to rainfall. E.g., humidity can be monitored using CMLs [1], as well as other types of phenomena such as fog [2] and different types of precipitation (snow, sleet) [3]. These further capabilities might be worthwhile to mention in the background.

[1] Rubin Y, Rostkier-Edelstein D, Chwala C, Alpert P. Challenges in Diurnal Humidity Analysis from Cellular Microwave Links (CML) over Germany. *Remote Sensing*. 2022; 14(10):2353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14102353>

[2] David, N., O. Sendik, H. Messer, and P. Alpert, 2015: Cellular Network Infrastructure: The Future of Fog Monitoring?. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 96, 1687–1698, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-13-00292.1> [3] Jonatan Ostrometzky, Dani Cherkassky, Hagit Messer, "Accumulated Mixed Precipitation Estimation Using Measurements from Multiple

Microwave Links", *Advances in Meteorology*, vol. 2015, Article ID 707646, 9 pages, 2015.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/707646>

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
